

TRANSLATION OF LITERARY TEXT - CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES

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Abstract. *Literary translation presents significant hurdles, distinct from other forms of translation, as it requires more than a simple word-for-word transcription. Preserving the artistic essence and imaginative quality of a literary work while effectively adapting it to the target language adds complexity to the process. In this article, we will explore the distinctive features and numerous obstacles encountered in literary translation.*

Keywords: *literary translation, poetic language, intertextuality, traverse linguistic boundaries.*

Аннотация. *Литературный перевод представляет собой значительные трудности, отличающиеся от других видов перевода, поскольку он требует большего, чем простая дословная транскрипция. Сохранение художественной сути и образного качества литературного произведения при эффективной адаптации его к языку перевода усложняет процесс. В этой статье мы рассмотрим отличительные особенности и различные сложности, возникающие при литературном переводе.*

Ключевые слова: *художественный перевод, поэтический язык, интертекстуальность, преодоление языковых границ.*

Annotatsiya. *Badiiy tarjima boshqa tarjima turlaridan farq qiladigan muhim qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqaradi, chunki u oddiy so'zma-so'z transkripsiyadan ko'proq narsani talab qiladi. Adabiy asarning badiiy mohiyatini, obrazlilik sifatini asrab-avaylash, uni o'rganilayotgan tilga samarali moslashtirish jarayonni murakkablashtiradi. Ushbu maqolada biz badiiy tarjima jarayonida yuzaga keladigan o'ziga xos xususiyatlar va turli qiyinchiliklarni ko'rib chiqamiz.*

Kalit so'zlar: *adabiy tarjima, she'riy til, intertekstuallik, lingvistik chegaralarni engib o'tish.*

Literature, with its rich tapestry of language, culture, and nuance, serves as a bridge between diverse communities worldwide. However, for literature to traverse linguistic boundaries and reach broader audiences, it often requires skilled translators who can capture the essence of the original work while adapting it into a different language. Translating literary works is a complex and multifaceted process fraught with challenges yet enriched with creative opportunities. In this article, we delve into the intricacies of literary translation, exploring the hurdles translators face and the various approaches they employ to surmount them.

Features of Literary Texts

Despite the challenges they pose, literary texts also possess distinctive features that enrich the translation process and enhance the reader's experience. One such feature is the use of language as a tool for artistic expression. Literary works often employ poetic language, vivid imagery, and evocative prose to convey complex emotions and ideas. Translators must strive to preserve the beauty and elegance of the original language while ensuring that the translated text maintains its aesthetic appeal and emotional resonance.

Literary texts also frequently explore universal themes and human experiences that transcend linguistic and cultural boundaries. Whether addressing love, loss, identity, or existential questions, these themes resonate with readers across cultures, making literary translation a powerful means of fostering cross-cultural understanding and empathy. Translators play a crucial

role in bridging these cultural divides, enabling readers to access and appreciate works of literature from around the world.

Additionally, literary texts often exhibit intertextuality, referencing and engaging with other works of literature, mythology, or historical events. Translators must be adept at recognizing and navigating these intertextual references, ensuring that the translated text retains its richness and depth of meaning. By preserving these connections, translators honor the legacy of the original work and facilitate a deeper engagement with its themes and motifs.

Challenges in Literary Translation

One of the foremost challenges in translating literary works lies in faithfully preserving the author's voice, style, and intent across languages. Every language possesses its unique cadences, idioms, and cultural references, making a direct, word-for-word translation virtually impossible. Translators must navigate these linguistic disparities with finesse, striving to retain the original work's literary merit and emotional resonance.

Cultural nuances pose another significant obstacle in literary translation. Certain concepts, jokes, or references may be deeply rooted in the cultural context of the source language, rendering them difficult to convey accurately in the target language. Translators must possess not only a profound understanding of both languages but also a keen awareness of the cultural intricacies embedded within the text.

Furthermore, literary works often contain wordplay, metaphors, and symbolism that defy straightforward translation. Maintaining the subtleties and layers of meaning inherent in such literary devices requires ingenuity and creativity on the part of the translator. Balancing fidelity to the original text with readability and coherence in the translated version is a delicate tightrope act that demands skill and artistry.

Approaches to Literary Translation

To tackle the challenges posed by literary translation, translators employ a variety of approaches tailored to the specific demands of each work. One such approach is known as "domestication," wherein the translator adapts the text to suit the linguistic and cultural conventions of the target audience. This approach prioritizes readability and accessibility, sometimes at the expense of fidelity to the original text.

Conversely, the "foreignization" approach seeks to preserve the foreignness of the source text, deliberately retaining linguistic and cultural elements that may be unfamiliar to the target audience. By maintaining a degree of distance from the target language and culture, foreignization aims to provide readers with a more authentic experience of the original work, albeit at the cost of potential comprehension hurdles.

Translators may also employ a combination of these approaches, depending on the nature of the text and the preferences of the target audience. Hybrid strategies, such as "adaptive translation," strike a balance between domestication and foreignization, endeavoring to capture the essence of the original while ensuring accessibility to the target readership.

Additionally, advancements in technology have facilitated the process of literary translation through tools such as machine translation and translation memory software. While these automated solutions can expedite the translation process, they often lack the nuanced understanding and creative insight of human translators, particularly when it comes to preserving the literary quality of the text.

The Importance of Creativity in Literary Translation

Although maintaining accuracy and loyalty to the original text remains paramount in literary translation, the application of creative adaptation can significantly enhance the process. Translators must navigate the delicate balance between staying true to the source material and ensuring that the text resonates with the target audience.

An instance where creative adaptation becomes crucial is when translators encounter idiomatic expressions or wordplay that lack direct equivalents in the target language. In such scenarios, translators may opt to employ similar idioms or wordplay in the target language that convey analogous meanings to the original expressions. This necessitates a degree of creativity as translators strive to capture the essence of the original while ensuring comprehension for the target readership.

Additionally, translators may find it necessary to modify the source material to align with the conventions and expectations of the target culture. For instance, a novel deeply entrenched in a specific cultural context may require adjustments to enhance its relatability for readers from different cultural backgrounds.

Moreover, the selection of words and phrasing in the translation offers another avenue for creative expression. While preserving the author's voice and tone is essential, translators must also consider the preferences and expectations of the target audience. This might involve incorporating colloquial language or adopting a distinct writing style to captivate the readership.

Nonetheless, it is imperative to ensure that any creative adaptations remain faithful to the author's original intent. Translators must refrain from taking liberties with the source material that could alter its fundamental meaning or misrepresent the author's intentions.

Thus, while maintaining accuracy and faithfulness to the source text is crucial in literary translation, the application of creative adaptation can significantly enrich the process. Translators must adeptly balance the task of accurately conveying the author's message with the goal of engaging and resonating with the target audience. Creative adaptation demands sensitivity to cultural disparities, linguistic nuances, and idiomatic expressions while upholding the integrity of the original work.

In conclusion, it can be summarized that translating literary works is a labor of love that requires not only linguistic proficiency but also a deep appreciation for the artistry and cultural significance of literature. Despite the myriad challenges inherent in the process, skilled translators employ various approaches to convey the beauty and complexity of literary masterpieces across linguistic boundaries. As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, the role of literary translation in fostering cross-cultural understanding and appreciation has never been more vital. By bridging the gaps between languages and cultures, translators serve as custodians of global literary heritage, enriching the lives of readers around the world with the transformative power of literature.

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